

Supporting Information

Reaction Outcome Critically Dependent on the Method of Workup: An Example from the Synthesis of 1-Isoquinolones

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^1H NMR
500 MHz,
DMSO- d_6

2a

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR
125.7 MHz,
DMSO- d_6

2a

^{19}F NMR
470 MHz,
DMSO- d_6

^1H NMR
500 MHz,
DMSO- d_6

8.59
8.35
8.35
8.35
8.32
8.25
8.25
8.24
8.24
8.12
8.12
8.11
8.11
8.10
7.92
7.92
7.91
7.91
7.90
7.89
7.89
7.86
7.86
7.85
7.85
7.84
7.84
7.82
7.82
7.81
7.81
7.80
7.79
7.79

3c

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR
125.7 MHz,
DMSO- d_6

150.45
147.23
141.08
138.40
132.28
132.28
129.70
129.44
129.19
128.94
128.26
127.65
127.65
125.97
125.94
125.91
125.88
125.80
125.67
125.67
123.32
123.16
118.12

3c

^{19}F NMR
470 MHz,
DMSO- d_6

3c

^1H NMR
500 MHz,
DMSO- d_6

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR
125.7 MHz,
DMSO- d_6

^1H NMR
500 MHz,
 CDCl_3

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR
125.7 MHz,
 CDCl_3

^{19}F NMR
470 MHz,
 CDCl_3

^1H NMR
500 MHz,
DMSO- d_6

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR
125.7 MHz,
DMSO- d_6

^1H NMR
500 MHz,
DMSO- d_6

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR
125.7 MHz,
DMSO- d_6

¹H NMR
500 MHz,
DMSO-d₆

¹³C{¹H} NMR
125.7 MHz,
DMSO-d₆

^{19}F NMR
470 MHz,
DMSO- d_6

^1H NMR
500 MHz,
DMSO- d_6

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR
125.7 MHz,
DMSO- d_6

Crystallography

Full-sets of diffraction data for **5a** were collected at 150(2)K with a Bruker D8-Venture diffractometer equipped with Mo (Mo/K α radiation; $\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) microfocus X-ray (I μ S) sources, Photon CMOS detector and Oxford Cryosystems cooling device was used for data collection.

The frames were integrated with the Bruker SAINT software package using a narrow-frame algorithm. Data were corrected for absorption effects using the Multi-Scan method (SADABS). Obtained data were treated by XT-version 2014/5 and SHELXL-2017/1 software implemented in APEX3 v2016.5-0 (Bruker AXS) system.^[S1]

Hydrogen atoms were mostly localized on a difference Fourier map, however to ensure uniformity of treatment of crystal, all hydrogen were recalculated into idealized positions (riding model) and assigned temperature factors H_{iso}(H) = 1.2 U_{eq} (pivot atom) or of 1.5U_{eq} (methyl). H atoms in methyl, methylene, moieties and hydrogen atoms in aromatic rings were placed with C-H distances of 0.96, 0.97 and 0.93 \AA , hydrogen atoms in N-H bonds were refined freely.

$R_{\text{int}} = \sum |F_o^2 - F_{o,\text{mean}}^2| / \sum F_o^2$, $\text{GOF} = [\sum (w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2) / (N_{\text{diffrs}} - N_{\text{params}})]^{1/2}$ for all data, $R(F) = \sum ||F_o| - |F_c|| / \sum |F_o|$ for observed data, $wR(F^2) = [\sum (w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2) / (\sum w(F_o^2)^2)]^{1/2}$ for all data.

Crystallographic data for structural analysis have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, CCDC no. 2065025. Copies of this information may be obtained free of charge from The Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EY, UK (fax: +44-1223-336033; e-mail: deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or www: <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk>).

The crystals were prepared by crystallization of **5a** from ethyl acetate by leaving a hot solution to stand at rt.

Table SI-1. Experimental details for 5a.

Crystal data	
Chemical formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O
M_r	252.31
Crystal system, space group	Triclinic, <i>P1</i>
Temperature (K)	150
a, b, c (Å)	8.3608 (3), 8.8135 (3), 9.6041 (3)
α, β, γ (°)	109.140 (1), 94.023 (1), 107.043 (1)
V (Å ³)	628.30 (4)
Z	2
Radiation type	Mo $K\alpha$
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.09
Crystal size (mm)	0.68 × 0.41 × 0.14
Data collection	
Diffractometer	Bruker D8 - Venture
Absorption correction	Multi-scan
T_{\min}, T_{\max}	0.690, 0.746
No. of measured, independent and observed [$I > 2\sigma(I)$] reflections	21557, 3127, 2681
R_{int}	0.037
$(\sin \theta/\lambda)_{\text{max}}$ (Å ⁻¹)	0.668
Refinement	
$R[F^2 > 2\sigma(F^2)], wR(F^2), S$	0.039, 0.107, 1.04
No. of reflections	3127
No. of parameters	181
H-atom treatment	H atoms treated by a mixture of independent and constrained refinement
$\Delta\rho_{\text{max}}, \Delta\rho_{\text{min}}$ (e Å ⁻³)	0.32, -0.23

Although more than four hundreds 3,4-dihydroisoquinolin-1(2*H*)-ones crystal structures are reported within the Cambridge Structural Database, only four of them resemble the structure of **5a** with an amino substitution at position 3.^[S2] The structure of **5a**, unambiguously determined by *sc*-XRD techniques, crystallize in triclinic system within centrosymmetric space group *P*-1 (Fig. SI-1). The interatomic distances very close to distances in analogous compounds mentioned above and comparable to appropriate separations found for organic compounds,^[S3] except of C2-N1 (Fig. SI-1 caption), which is significantly elongated due the ring tension. Surprisingly enough, the N-H and amido groups does not have the expected H-bridging contact, instead of which only the C=O...H-C weak interactions are the structure making for **5a** supramolecular architecture.

Figure SI-1. ORTEP drawing for **5a**. Thermal ellipsoids are drawn at the 40% probability level. Selected interatomic distances [Å]: O1-C1 1.2365(13), N1-C1 1.3594(13), N1-C10 1.4608(14), N1-C2 1.5012(13), C1-C5 1.4884 (14), C2-N2 1.4504 (13), C2-C3 1.5307(15), C2-C11 1.5352(14), C3-C4 1.4935(15).

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